

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№3

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

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*Elektron nashr. 621 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 11-martda ruxsat etildi.*

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- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

Improving the efficiency of investment activity in oil and gas enterprises.....	24
Raxmatova M.G., G'ofurov Sh.N.	
Organization of control and evaluation of effectiveness in international companies.....	30
Nasimov Bakhtiyor Vasiyevich	
Xalqaro standartlarning korxonaga eksportini oshishidagi ahamiyati.....	35
Sobitov Diyor Abbralxonovich	
Erkin iqtisodiy zonalar boshqaruvining tashkiliy tuzilmasini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	40
Ataismatov Iqboljon Zumratjonovich	
Xorazm viloyatida turizm infratuzilmasini innovatsion rivojlantirish ko'rsatkichlarini ekonometrik modellashtirish va prognozlashtirishning ba'zi masalari.....	46
Jumaniyazova Ro'za Quvondiq qizi	
Tijorat banklarining moliyaviy barqarorligini mustahkamlash.....	60
Rasulov Muxammad Bobur Fazliddin o'g'li	
Economic analysis of investment activity of enterprises.....	66
Shermatov Akhror Abduhakimovich	
Kichik biznesni rivojlantirishda innovatsion faoliyatni moliyalashtirish yo'nalishlari.....	72
Z. Rahimova	
Влияние углеродного следа на экологическую устойчивость узбекистана.....	76
Саттарова Барно Шухратовна	
Moliya bozori dastaklari orqali xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etish modellarining uslubiy asoslari.....	84
Ibragimov G'anijon G'ayratovich	
Maqsdadli tushumlarning audit obyekti sifatidagi tasnifi va tavsifi.....	90
Ne'matov Oybek Ismatullayevich, Qambarov Abduazizbek	
Bank majburiyatlari tushunchasi, uning mazmuni va mohiyati.....	96
Muminova Parvina Ilhom qizi	
Sanoat korxonalariga berilayotgan soliq imtiyozlari ma'murchiligini ta'minlash borasida amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar samaradorligi.....	100
Turabov Ulug'bek Olimjonovich	
Tur operatorlari va sayohat agentliklarida xarajatlar va foyda tahlili va uning turlari.....	106
Taniyev Ahmadjon Bahromovich	
O'zbekistonda kredit bozorini rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	113
Salimov Burxon Abubakirovich	
Social media marketing as a key strategy in modern business.....	125
Najimova Bakhtigul Abdilkasim qizi	
O'zbekistonda yashil mahsulotlar eksportini rivojlantirish orqali barqaror iqtisodiy o'sish va xalqaro integratsiyani ta'minlash.....	129
Radjabov Bunyod Abduxalilovich	
Оценка и управление рисками в проектах строительства энергетических объектов.....	136
Махматулов Жамшед Бахтиёрович	
Iqtisodiyotda ko'chmas mulk bozori hamda uning xususiyatlari.....	140
Ibragimov Qobil To'xtamishovich, Raimkulov Sherali O'rozdavlatovich, G'ffarov Husayn Aliyor o'g'li, Ismoilov Davronjon Ilxomjon o'g'li, Tashpulatova Shaxnoza Tursunpulatovna	
Ekologik turizmning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ta'siri va uni rivojlantirish istiqbollari (Jizzax viloyati misolida).....	144
Isomiddinov Sherzod Sirojiddin o'g'li	
Ways to improve personnel policy in improving the quality of financial services provided by financial institutions.....	148
Ergashev Umidjon Ibragimovich	
Qo'shilgan qiymat solig'ining budjet daromadlarini shakllantirishdagi ahamiyati.....	152
Djabbarov Anvar Muxammadsaliyevich	

Tadbirkorlik subyektlarining barqarorlik reytingini aniqlash va ulardan samarali foydalanish yo'llari	157
Abdullayev Zafarbek Safibullayevich	
Tovar-moddiy zaxiralar auditini tashkil qilish masalalari	164
Turmanqulov Norpo'lat Sa'dullayevich, Botirov Lazizbek Botirovich	
O'zbekiston tijorat banklari faoliyatida aktivlar daromadligini oshirish masalalari.....	168
Saxibjonov Muzaffar Salijanovich	
Organization of control and evaluation of effectiveness in international companies.....	174
Nasimov Bakhtiyor Vasiyevich	
Strategic growth of global companies in contemporary environments.....	179
Djurabaev Otabek Djurabayevich	
Directions for management of the tax system.....	184
Sharokhmatov Abdurakhim Abdulamitovich	
Davlat korxonalarida moliyaviy samaradorlik va uni boshqarish tizimini takomillashtirish yo'nalishlari.....	188
Qarshiyev Nodirbek Olim o'g'li	
Проблемы, модели и методы оптимизации управления товарными запасами	193
Бабаджанов Шопулат Шомашрабович	
Literature review: the significance of digitization to management credit activity of commercial banks	200
Jo'rayev Eldor Berdibekovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasining davlat budjeti.....	205
Ajibaeva Raiya Maxsudovna	
Yashil iqtisodiyot kontsepsiyasining shakillanishi, taraqqiyot bosqichlari va uning dolzarbligi.....	212
Kodirov Javlonbek Nematullayevich	
Bank plastik kartalari orqali masofaviy xizmatlarni takomillashtirish.....	219
Abdullayeva Dildora Qudratovna, Abdullayev Baxodirjon Valijon o'g'li, Almuratova Nurliolmasoy Naim qizi	
O'zbekistonda iqtisodiy o'sishni ekonometrik modellashtirish	223
Shamsiyeva Feruza Muratxodjayevna	
Mahalla faoliyati ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlarini tahlil qilishning nazariy asoslari.....	232
Aliqulov Ravshan Shodiyor o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda lizing bozori tahlili.....	237
Boyev Bekzodjon Jo'raqul o'g'li, Shavkatov Behruz Rustam o'g'li	
Chakana savdoni rivojlantirishning mintaqaviy xususiyatlari	241
Ismoilov Shohjahon O'tkir o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda tibbiy xizmatlarning rivojlanish tendensiyalari, tarkibiy tuzilish tasnifi va marketing segmentlari	244
Axmedov Zafarjon A'zamovich	
Мировой опыт и перспективы развития свободно экономических зон в Республике Узбекистан.....	250
Кадирова Истора Кадирова	
Перспективы реформирования налоговой системы Республики Узбекистан в условиях глобализации.....	254
Буранова Лола Вахобовна, Садиков Искандар Гайратович	
O'zbekiston 2030 strategiyasi – islohotlar tizimligida ipoteka kreditining dolzarbligi.....	263
A'zamxo'jayeva Nihola	
O'zbekistonda sug'urta mexanizmlarini rivojlantirish istiqbollari	267
Shoraximova Zilola Nosirdjanovna	
Biologiya va tibbiyotda matematik statistika	271
Voxidov Alikul Melitoshevich	
Viloyatda chorvachilik mahsulotlarini o'tgan yilga nisbatan o'zgarishi.....	283
Azimov Allaberdin O'rinovich, Begaliyeva Madina Abdusamatovna	
Servis korxonalarida mobil ilovalar yordamida interaktiv xizmatlar yaratish	289
Ne'matov Nizom Ismatullayevich	
Oziq-ovqat ta'minot zanjiri tushunchasi va uning zamonaviy tendensiyalari.....	293
Nazarova A.N	

Влияние искусственного интеллекта при разработке стратегических программ на экономическое развитие страны.....	300
Каримова Нуржахон Олим кизи	
Kichik va o'rta biznesda moliyaviy menejment: muammolar va yechimlar	306
Saidvaliyeva Nigora Ziyodillayevna	
Теоретико-правовая характеристика экономических отношений	313
Фарход Махмудович Тиркашев, Исломжон Жамшедович Жамшедов	
Cash flow reporting in Uzbekistan: national accounting standards and international standards application	318
Ochilov Ilyos Keldiyorovich	
Tadbirkorlik salohiyatini rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari va takomillashtirish mexanizmlari	324
Baxtiyor Xabibullayev Abdulvoxid o'g'li	
Получение долгосрочного кредита и определение его размера для привлечения лизинга	330
Латипова Шахноза Махмудовна	
Ko'chmas mulk solig'ining ko'chmas mulk bozori tendensiyalariga ta'siri	335
To'lakov Ulug'bek Toshmamatovich	
Rivojlangan mamlakatlarning davlat qarzi va uni boshqarishdagi tajribasini tahlil qilishga ilmiy yondashuv	343
Suynov Dilmurod Xolmuradovich, Abdurahmonova Feruzabonu	
Эффективный инновационный менеджмент в системе здравоохранения Республики Узбекистан.....	353
Абдурахманов З.М.	
Islom moliyasining O'zbekistondagi o'rni va O'zbekiston Respublikasining islomiy tashkilotlar va banklar bilan aloqasi	356
Otajonova Charosxon Polvonquli qizi, Elboyev Otajon Polvonquliyevich	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlarida innovatsion faoliyatni rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari.....	361
Oxunjonova Madina Isoqjonovna	
Основные задачи обеспечения цифровой информационной безопасности в образовательном процессе	365
Иззатилла Пулатов Кудратиллаевич	
Tijorat banklarida komplaens nazoratni takomillashtirish.....	373
Muminova Marguba Mamirkulovna	
Kichik biznes uchun soliq imtiyozlari va ularning samaradorligi.....	378
Sarvar Ochilov	
Xalqaro moliyaviy tashkilotlarning davlat iqtisodiy rivojlanishidagi o'rni	387
Raxmonova Dildora Ergash qizi	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida kreditning iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishdagi o'rni	395
Eshqobulova Charos O'roq qizi	
Mintaqa sanoat korxonalarida investitsiya jarayonlari rivojlanish tendensiyasining statistik tahlili.....	399
Quvatova Gulzoda Faxriddin qizi	
Natijalarga yo'naltirilgan budjetlashtirish samarali budjet menejmentining omili sifatida	403
N. Sheraliev	
O'zbekistonda kichik biznesning rivojlanish tendensiyalari va istiqbollari	408
Salayev Jasurbek Komilovich	
Features and prospects for the development of digital marketing in Uzbekistan.....	414
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
Анализ динамики импорта узбекистана в 2017–2024 годах с учетом индекса сложности продукции (PCI)	418
Жабборова Нодира Холмурод кизи	
O'zbekistonning kredit riskini baholash: iqtisodiy barqarorlik va xavf omillari tahlili	422
Hakimov Hakimjon Abdullo o'g'li	
Investitsion jozibadorlikni oshirish – korxonalarining raqobatbardoshligini oshirishning muhim shartidir	426
Karimova Dilafuz Sadirdin qizi	

Sanoat korxonalarida innovatsion faollikni oshirish omillari.....	431
Qo'ziyev Shodiyor Qilichboy o'g'li, Xakimov Javohir Hamza o'g'li, Turganbaev Nursultan Bayram o'g'li, Masharipov Rasulbek Jo'rabekovich, Xasanov Ruslan Raxmatovich, Nurullayev Jasurbek Davronbekovich	
Теоретические основы формирования понятия «финансовая стабильность».....	437
Алиева Сусанна Сейрановна	
Developing the labor market and strategies for reducing unemployment.....	442
Tojiyeva Muhabbatxon Mansurjon qizi, Elmurodov Mukhammadkodir Nurmuhammad	
Iqlim o'zgarishi sharoitida raqamli texnologiyalar orqali qishloq xo'jaligida samaradorlikni oshirish yo'llari.....	450
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Ochilov Ilhom Sayitqulovich, Sayfullayeva Ruxshona Farrux qizi	
To'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalarning sanoatni rivojlantirishdagi roli.....	458
Samijonov Musobek G'ayratjon o'g'li	
Ishlab chiqarish korxonalarida risklarni boshqarishning asosiy yo'nalishlari va rivojlanish istiqbollari.....	466
Muxitdinov Shuhrat Ziyavitdinovich	
Ovqatlanish xizmatlarini rivojlantirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlaridan foydalanish va samaradorligini oshirishning asosiy yo'nalishlari.....	470
Ravshanov Zaxiriddin Ibragimovich	
Ta'lim jarayonida sun'iy intellektdan foydalanishning ahamiyati.....	477
Safayeva Dilafuz Ruzmatovna, Karimov Abrorjon Shavkat o'g'li	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarini xarajatlarini rejalashtirish va moliyalashtirish: amaldagi holat tahlili.....	482
Bauyetdinov M.J., Medetbayeva D.T	
Tijorat banklarida foiz risklarini baholash va boshqarish.....	487
Karimov Mardon Akram o'g'li	
Zamonaviy sharoitda bank innovatsiyalaridan foydalanishning istiqbolli yo'nalishlari.....	494
Xodjimamedov Akmal Ashurovich	
A local perspective on sustainable supply chain management in Uzbekistan.....	501
Oybek Rafukjonkhajiev	
Raqamli texnologiyalar orqali sug'urta kompaniyalar marketing faoliyatini takomillashtirish.....	505
Rashidova Dildora Rasul qizi	
O'zbekistonning strategik rivojlanish davrida investitsiyalarning o'rni.....	511
Akbaraliyeva Aziza Maxmadali qizi	
O'zbekiston media bozori: rivojlanishi va afzalliklari.....	516
Qodirov Obidjon Olim o'g'li	
Порядок учета скидок в бухгалтерском учете на основе МСФО.....	520
Камолова Феруза Кахрамоновна	
Tijorat banklari transformatsiyasini amalga oshirishda qimmatli qog'ozlar bozorida foydalanishning xorijiy tajribasi.....	525
Bobur Abrorovich Yusupov	
Neft va gaz sanoati korxonalari resurslardan samarali foydalanishning xorijiy tajribalari tahlili.....	533
Sonayev Sanjar Nurmatovich	
Оценка социально-экономического воздействия железнодорожных проектов.....	539
Хужаяров Бекзод Баходир угли	
Rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlarda islom mikromoliyalashning innovatsion mexanizmlari va xalqaro tajriba.....	544
Sharipova Maxliyoxon Baxtiyor qizi	
Iqtisodiy samaradorlik tushunchasining ilmiy- nazariy tahlili.....	548
Ibragimov Zukhriddin Sayfutdinovich	
Ipoteka kreditlarini moliyalashtirishda banklarning o'rni va istiqbollari.....	552
Muhitdinov Ulug'bek Diyorovich	
Mintaqaviy mehnat bozorini shakllanishining shart-sharoitlari, omillari, o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va prinsiplari.....	556
Amonov Navro'zxon Saloxiddin o'g'li	
Development of digital marketing for sustainable tourism development in Uzbekistan.....	560
Nasibabonu Abdurakhmonovna Akramova	

Kichik biznes subyektlarining raqobatbardoshligini oshirishga qaratilgan innovatsion yondashuvlar	565
Ibragimov Ulmas	
Tijorat banklarining moliyaviy xavfsizligini ta'minlashning dolzarb masalalari	569
Akbarov Behzodxon Ulug'bek o'g'li	
Amerika qo'shma shtatlarida federal zaxira tizimi tomonidan amalga oshirilgan noan'anaviy pul-kredit siyosati.....	574
Djumonov Dilshod Safaroliyevich	
Intellectual mulkning ishlab chiqarishdagi ahamiyati	581
Farhod Mahmudovich Tirkashyev, Azizbek Umid o'g'li Abduvaliyev	
Tijorat banklari moliyaviy barqarorligini baholashning xorijiy davlatlar tajribasi	585
Sattarova Gulshan Muxiddinovna	
Qimmatli qog'ozlar bozorida moliyaviy xavfsizlik: investorlar misolida.....	589
Boysunov Jamshid Baxriddin ug'li	
Amaliy-ilmiy tadqiqotlarning mazmuni, asosiy maqsadlari va qo'llanilish shakllari.....	593
Raupov Jamshid Rashidovich, Kaxramonov Zafar Kaxramonovich	
Tijorat banklarida korporativ boshqaruvni takomillashtirishning dolzarb masalalari	597
Ergashev Olim Kenjayevich	
Islom darchalari asosida moliyalashtirishni joriy etish istiqbollari	602
Gulyamova Shaxnoza Gafurdjanovna	
Влияние финансовых технологий на трансформацию страхового рынка.....	606
Тангирбердиева Гулчехра Рахимжановна	
Tadbirkorlik faoliyatini rivojlanishida mamlakatimiz iqtisodiyotini holati tahlili	611
Muradova Maxliyoxon Ravshanovna	
Foreign experience in the formation of banking assets in improving the efficiency of the activities of commercial banks.....	615
Ibrohimov Davronbek Muhammadi ogli	

INTRODUCTION

Commercial banks play a crucial role in the economic system, ensuring financial stability and supporting sustainable economic growth. Bank assets are essential components of a commercial bank's operations, directly linked to its profitability, liquidity, and financial stability. The effective management and optimization of bank assets are vital for the successful operation of commercial banks, especially in the face of global economic conditions and market changes.

Foreign countries have implemented various successful methods and strategies in managing and optimizing bank assets, which have proven effective in improving the performance of commercial banks. Specifically, banks operating in advanced economies utilize modern approaches, such as asset diversification, the introduction of innovative technologies, risk management systems, and capital strengthening. These approaches not only enhance the profitability of banks but also help ensure financial stability and maintain continuous economic growth.

This article analyzes the most effective strategies for asset formation and management based on foreign experience. It discusses how Uzbekistan's commercial banks can benefit from these practices to improve their operational efficiency and optimize bank assets. The aim of this paper is to propose best practices for managing bank assets and improving the efficiency of commercial bank activities in Uzbekistan, based on foreign experiences.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

The evolution of banking regulation and its impact on the efficiency of commercial banks can be traced through several significant historical periods. One of the most pivotal times was the "First Age of Globalization," which spanned from 1870 to 1914. This era witnessed the latter part of the Industrial Revolution, characterized by an expansion of large-scale capital investments, such as in railways, which facilitated a deepening of global finance and an increase in cross-border borrowing and lending by banks [1][2]. These developments played a crucial role in financing large-scale projects that underpinned economic prosperity during this period. However, the onset of World War I brought this growth to a standstill, marking a critical turning point in banking practices and regulatory environments [3][4]. As nations grappled with the economic fallout of the war, regulatory oversight became increasingly essential to protect investors and consumers from the risks associated with unregulated financial activities. In the modern context, the regulation of the asset management industry highlights the ongoing importance of oversight in maintaining market stability and investor confidence. The Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) and the Financial Industry Regulatory Authority (FINRA) play key roles in governing asset management firms, particularly those managing over \$110 million in assets [5]. This regulatory framework is crucial for mitigating risks and preventing fraud in an industry that provides advisory and financial planning services. Moreover, a comparative analysis of banking regulatory practices, particularly among the BRICS nations from 2000 to 2019, indicates that regulatory environments have a significant impact on the efficiency and sustainability of domestic banks, especially in developing economies [6][7]. This historical perspective underscores the vital role that regulatory frameworks have played and continue to play in shaping the landscape of banking and finance globally.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The primary goal of this research is to study foreign experiences in the formation and management of banking assets, as well as to analyze how these methods can be applied to improve the efficiency of commercial banks in Uzbekistan. The following methodological approaches and techniques were employed in the research:

Historical and comparative analysis. In the first stage of the research, methods and strategies for managing bank assets in foreign banking systems were studied in a historical context. This helped in understanding the practical approaches used in different countries for asset management and their results.

Comparative method. A comparison was made between foreign banks and commercial banks in Uzbekistan in terms of asset management and efficiency. This approach allowed for the identification of common and unique features and helped select the most effective methods from foreign practices that could be applied to Uzbekistan's banking system.

Case studies and practice analysis. Successful strategies and techniques of foreign banks in managing banking assets were illustrated through case studies. By analyzing these cases, the study showed how banks have improved their efficiency by implementing specific methods and innovations.

Expert opinions and interviews. Interviews were conducted with bankers and financial experts. The insights gathered from these experts became a crucial resource in formulating the conclusions of the study.

Additionally, the practical experiences of bankers and analysts provided valuable perspectives on both theoretical and practical aspects.

Comparative analysis. A comparative analysis was carried out between commercial banks in Uzbekistan and foreign banks to identify key differences. This analysis, through evaluating foreign strategies and the factors affecting asset management, helped determine the methods that could be implemented in Uzbekistan's banking system.

The results of this research, based on foreign experience and practices, will help develop optimal asset management strategies for commercial banks in Uzbekistan and will contribute to enhancing their efficiency and ensuring financial stability.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The evolution of international banking activity reflects significant historical trends and shifts, particularly as foreign banks have established a foothold in various markets. This has led to a transformation in local lending practices, with foreign bank branches and subsidiaries increasingly dominating local claims in developing regions. From the year 2000 to 2010, international banking activities among industrialized nations saw a remarkable increase, with the volume of cross-border lending rising from less than \$5 trillion to over \$15 trillion, marking a period of rapid expansion and innovation in banking practices, including the use of derivatives and credit commitments [8][9][10].

In the context of improving banking efficiency, regulatory frameworks have been pivotal. Many countries, particularly in Africa and the Asian and Pacific regions, have engaged with the International Monetary Fund (IMF) to develop Financial Soundness Indicators (FSIs) that align with international standards. This initiative not only aimed to bolster the financial health of these economies but also facilitated the supervision of both financial and non-financial sectors, demonstrating a collaborative approach to enhancing banking efficiency even in fragile states like South Sudan [11][10]. By mid-2016, 21 countries had become FSI reporters, providing accessible data for global investors, which underscores the impact of regulatory harmonization on banking efficiency [11].

The Role of Basel III.

The implementation of Basel III has further shaped the landscape of international banking by requiring banks to maintain higher-quality capital and liquidity standards. This framework is designed to mitigate the risk of financial crises by ensuring that banks are equipped with sufficient buffers to absorb shocks. The emphasis on robust capital structures and stringent risk management under Basel III has fostered a more resilient banking system globally, enhancing the efficiency and stability of commercial banks in a challenging financial environment [12][13]. The compliance of banks with Basel III standards illustrates a proactive approach to maintaining financial soundness and protecting against future crises, which ultimately contributes to the overall efficiency of banking operations internationally [12][13].

The efficiency of commercial banks is significantly influenced by various factors, including regulatory policies, market conditions, and management practices. Studies have shown that foreign bank entry can enhance financial efficiency, particularly in developing countries. For instance, research indicates that while foreign banks can improve the overall efficiency of the banking sector, they may also destabilize smaller domestic banks, presenting both opportunities and challenges for local institutions [14][15].

Regulatory policies play a crucial role in shaping the efficiency of banking markets. A comprehensive examination of 678 commercial banks across 21 European Union countries reveals that effective regulatory frameworks can lead to enhanced market efficiency [16]. These policies help establish a competitive environment that encourages innovation and performance improvements among banks.

Another critical aspect impacting bank efficiency is diversification. A study focusing on commercial banks in six ASEAN countries from 2007 to 2014 found that diversification strategies positively affected both cost and profit efficiency [17]. By spreading risks and enhancing service offerings, banks can achieve greater operational effectiveness and profitability.

The quality of Human Resource Management (HRM) practices is also pivotal for enhancing banking efficiency. Investment in employee competencies and motivation directly correlates with service quality, which is essential for maintaining competitiveness in the banking sector [18]. Banks that prioritize HRM practices tend to experience improved efficiency as motivated employees deliver better services to clients.

Effective risk management is vital for banks to sustain their efficiency levels. Banks implement robust risk management strategies to identify, evaluate, and mitigate potential operational and investment risks. This involves separating fraud risk management from compliance risk management, ensuring that dedicated teams address specific risks adequately [19][20]. Furthermore, third-party risk management practices are essential

in assessing and mitigating risks arising from outsourcing services to external vendors, thereby maintaining operational integrity and compliance [20].

The formation of banking assets and the improvement of efficiency within commercial banks face several challenges and limitations, particularly influenced by regulatory frameworks and market dynamics.

Regulatory compliance is essential for banks, as it ensures that their operations adhere to legal and regulatory requirements [21]. However, the constantly changing landscape of compliance rules necessitates that compliance teams remain agile. They must continuously update their strategies to adapt to new regulations, which can strain resources and complicate operational processes [22][23] (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Severe enforcement actions issued to US banks since 2020.

Data compiled Aug 29, 2023.

Analysis includes US commercial banks, and savings and loan associations. Excludes bank holding companies, thrift holding companies and credit unions.

Severe enforcement actions include prompt corrective action directives, cease and desist orders, consent orders and formal agreements that were issued and made public by federal regulatory agencies, including those severe enforcement actions that were later terminated.

*Third quarter 2023 data is through Aug. 29, 2023.

Source: S&P Global Market Intelligence.

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A significant challenge within compliance departments is resource constraints. This includes not only financial resources but also human capital. Many institutions struggle to maintain sufficient staff trained in compliance due to the high demand for expertise in a complex regulatory environment [22][24]. Consequently, banks may find it difficult to effectively implement and manage compliance measures, potentially leading to lapses that could expose them to regulatory penalties.

As banks engage in cross-border transactions, they encounter unique compliance challenges that arise from navigating a complex web of international regulations. This complexity can hinder efficiency and profitability, as institutions must invest significant resources to understand and comply with diverse regulatory requirements across different jurisdictions [22][24]. The intricate nature of these regulations can also lead to inconsistencies in compliance practices, further complicating the overall management of banking assets.

Effective risk management is crucial in addressing the challenges of compliance. Banks must proactively identify and assess compliance risks, implementing robust controls to mitigate these risks. This requires a comprehensive understanding of both internal operations and external regulatory expectations [25][26]. However, without the necessary resources and expertise, institutions may struggle to develop and execute effective risk management strategies, potentially exposing them to increased operational risks and financial penalties [27].

Finally, while regulation serves to protect consumers and maintain market stability, excessive regulatory burdens can impede the cost efficiency of banking operations. Striking a balance between maintaining adequate regulatory oversight and allowing banks the flexibility to operate efficiently remains a critical challenge [28]. Over-

regulation can stifle innovation and competitiveness in the banking sector, limiting the potential for commercial banks to enhance their asset formation strategies and overall effectiveness.

One of the foundational best practices in improving the efficiency of commercial banks involves the establishment of clear and comprehensive policies and procedures. It is crucial for these policies to be continuously reviewed and updated to ensure compliance with new laws and regulations. Moreover, transparency is key; policies should be communicated across the organization to ensure that every team member is aware of them and can act accordingly [29][30][31][32][33].

Implementing strong training programs is another vital practice that helps to set clear expectations for both employees and management. While these programs should be accessible to all employees, specialized training must be provided to those in key compliance roles to ensure a deeper understanding of specific regulatory requirements and best practices in banking [29][30][31][32][33].

Incorporating automation into compliance and operational processes is increasingly recognized as an effective strategy for enhancing efficiency. Automation not only streamlines operations but also helps to minimize human error and ensures that compliance procedures are consistently followed. This can lead to more accurate reporting and a stronger overall compliance posture [29][30][31][32][33]. These best practices are essential for commercial banks looking to enhance their operational efficiency and ensure effective management of banking assets in line with regulatory standards.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Foreign experience in the formation of banking assets plays a pivotal role in enhancing the efficiency of commercial banks worldwide. As global banking practices evolve, international influences have shaped local banking sectors, particularly in developing economies where foreign banks have introduced innovative lending practices and competitive dynamics. This cross-border interaction has not only improved financial efficiency but has also raised significant challenges for domestic institutions, leading to debates on the stability and sustainability of local banking systems amidst foreign competition. [1][2]

The increasing significance of regulatory frameworks in banking cannot be overstated. In the wake of economic crises, robust regulatory measures have emerged as essential tools for safeguarding financial markets and ensuring the soundness of banking operations. Notable examples include the Basel III standards, which require banks to maintain higher capital and liquidity reserves, fostering greater resilience in the global banking landscape. Moreover, collaborations with organizations like the International Monetary Fund (IMF) have enabled many countries to adopt Financial Soundness Indicators, aligning local banking regulations with international standards to enhance efficiency and attract foreign investment. [3][4][5]

Despite the advantages of foreign participation and regulatory compliance, the entry of foreign banks can destabilize local financial markets, particularly affecting smaller domestic banks. Studies indicate that while foreign banks can elevate overall banking efficiency, their presence may also lead to increased competition that challenges the viability of local institutions. [6][7]

Furthermore, the complex interplay between regulatory burdens and operational efficiency poses ongoing challenges for commercial banks, necessitating a delicate balance between maintaining compliance and fostering innovation. [8][9]

Ultimately, the formation of banking assets through foreign experiences underscores a dynamic interplay of opportunities and challenges for commercial banks. As they navigate the global financial landscape, the implications of regulatory policies, market conditions, and international collaborations continue to shape the effectiveness of banking operations and the stability of financial systems worldwide. [10][11][12]

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IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 3

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>
